

Synthetic, Structural and Antimicrobial Studies of some Macrocyclic Ligands and their Copper(II) Complexes

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Four new macrocyclic complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{DPIH})(\text{BF}_4)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{DPDH})(\text{BF}_4)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{DCIH})(\text{BF}_4)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DCPDH})(\text{BF}_4)_2$, where DPIH = 2,6-diacetylpyridine-*N*-iminodiacetylhydrazone, DPDH = 2,6-diacetylpyridine-*N*-pyridine-2,6-dicarboxyloxyhydrazone, DCIH = 2,6-pyridinedicarbonyldichloride-*N*-iminodiacetylhydrazone and DCPDH = 2,6-pyridinedicarbonyldichloride-*N*-pyridine-2,6-dicarboxyloxyhydrazone, have been synthesised. The *in vitro* antimicrobial studies revealed that the macrocyclic complexes are potentially active against a few bacteria and fungi and exhibit greater biocidal effect as compared to the ligand fragments.

Macrocyclic compounds are ideally applicable as complexing agents and ion-chelating resins. The selectivity of cyclic antibiotics toward cations has commercial application, e.g. valinomycin in ion-selective electrodes¹. 6-Hexadecyl-1,4,8,11-tetraaza cyclotetradecane-5,7-dione selectively encloses copper(II) and is found potentially useful for the separation of Cu^{II} by solvent extraction². The Cu^{II} complexes of the macrocyclic ligand 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaazaoctadecane (hexacyclon)³ have been isolated and the N-containing analogue of 18-crown-6, has been explored with reference to its metal complexes⁴. Recently, it has been used as an extracting agent for different metal ions⁵.

Hence, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some new macrocyclic chelates of Cu^{II} by the condensation of the dihydrazides of iminodiacetic acid/pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid with 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 2,6-pyridinedicarbonyldichloride.

Results and Discussion

All the coloured solid complexes (Table I) are stable at room temperature, and soluble in DMSO, DMF and propylene glycol but insoluble in common organic solvents. Their molar conductance values (107.60 – $110.50 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicate their electrolytic nature.

The IR spectra of all the ligand fragments reveal sharp and prominent bands at 3150 (NH), 1710 (C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} (NH_2). A sharp band is observed at 2900 cm^{-1} (CH_2) in the spectrum of IMDA dihydrazide.

The $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ transitions are observed around 1050 cm^{-1} . Also, the pyridine ring deformation bands appear at 450 (out-of-plane) and 630 cm^{-1} (in-plane) in the spectrum of PDA dihydrazide. In the IR spectra of metal complexes, the ν_{NH} band (3150 cm^{-1}) does not shift, thereby ruling out the coordination of nitrogen of NH with the central metal atom. However, the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band experiences a negative shift by 40 – 50 cm^{-1} appearing at 1660 cm^{-1} , while the position of $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ band is shifted to higher wavenumbers (1080 cm^{-1}). These observations lead to presume the involvement of amide oxygen of C=O and the nitrogen of N-N in complexation. On the other hand, the pyridine ring deformation bands show a positive shift by 20 – 30 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes. This is clear from their appearance at 480 (out-of-plane) and 650 cm^{-1} (in-plane). This shift predicts the role of pyridinyl nitrogen in complexation.

The copper chelates reveal an intense band at 1590 cm^{-1} due to the formation of C-N bond in the complexes. This results due to the condensation of acetyl groups of carbonyl compounds with the dihydrazides.

The IR spectra of the metal complexes exhibit some new bands which do not exist in the spectra of ligand fragments. In the spectra of all the complexes, the bands appearing at 460 , 450 and 380 – 370 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the coordination of azomethine and pyridinyl nitrogen on one hand and amide and carbonyl oxygen on the other, thus supporting the formation of M-N

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour, m.p. °C)	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Cu
IDADH (White, 163)	C ₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₅	29.44 (29.81)	6.33 (6.83)	42.84 (43.47)	—
PDADH (White, 199)	C ₇ H ₉ O ₂ N ₅	42.49 (43.07)	4.17 (4.61)	35.09 (35.89)	—
M(DPIH)(BF ₄) ₂ (Green, 240)	Cu[C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆](BF ₄) ₂	28.77 (29.70)	2.88 (3.04)	15.15 (15.99)	41.63 (12.09)
M(DPDH)(BF ₄) ₂ (Green, 300)	Cu[C ₁₆ H ₁₄ (O ₂ N ₆)](BF ₄) ₂	33.99 (34.34)	2.41 (2.50)	14.84 (15.02)	10.79 (11.35)
M(DCIII)(BF ₄) ₂ (Green, 236)	Cu[C ₁₁ H ₁₀ (O ₄ N ₆)](BF ₄) ₂	24.54 (25.04)	1.79 (1.89)	15.37 (15.93)	11.61 (12.04)
M(DCPDH)(BF ₄) ₂ (Green, 254)	Cu[C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ N ₆](BF ₄) ₂	29.28 (29.83)	1.34 (1.42)	14.22 (14.91)	11.04 (11.27)

and M–O bonds in the complexes.

The broad bands at 15 800–17 950 and 30 600–28 150 cm⁻¹ are observed in the electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes. The former may be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions, suggesting thereby an octahedral geometry for these complexes⁶, and the latter can be attributed to L → M charge transfer band.

Antimicrobial study: Both the ligand fragments and their respective metal chelates were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity using serial dilution method against two bacteria, viz. *Escherichia coli* (gram negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram positive) [incubation period 24 h at 37°] and two fungi, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* [incubation period 96 h at 28°].

The test solutions of iminodiacetic acid dihydrazide (IDADH) and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide (PDADH) were prepared in propylene glycol and those of their metal complexes in DMSO diluted with culture media to give the required drug concentration in 2.5% DMSO. The ligand fragments IDADH and PDADH exhibited equal biocidal effect against *S. aureus* (Table 2). On the other hand, the activity varied to some extent in case of *E. coli*, being more for PDADH as compared to IDADH. Both the ligand fragments exhibited equal activity against the fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. The metal chelates showed enhanced activity against all the microorganisms. The enhanced

TABLE 2 – MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (MIC) VALUES IN MOLAR CONCENTRATIONS ($\times 10^{-4}$) OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.986	0.986	0.986	0.986
IDADH	6.210	6.210	6.210	6.210
PDADH	2.560	5.120	5.120	5.120
Cu(DPIH)(BF ₄) ₂	0.238	0.119	0.119	0.119
Cu(DPDH)(BF ₄) ₂	0.238	0.238	0.476	0.238
Cu(DCIII)(BF ₄) ₂	0.119	0.238	0.238	0.238
Cu(DCPDH)(BF ₄) ₂	0.238	0.476	0.476	0.476

biological activities of the macrocyclic chelates as compared with the ligand fragments can be explained through the following generalisations: (i) increasing biological activity might have been due to more liposolubility of the metal chelates, (ii) foreign metal ion of the more liposoluble metal complexes composing the macrocyclic ring might have been replaced by the metal ion present in biological enzymic systems, and (iii) combined activity effect of the ligand molecule and the metal atom might have multiplied the biocidal effect.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Iminodiacetic acid dihydrazide and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid dihydrazide were synthesised from their

corresponding dimethyl esters of the acids and hydrazine hydrate by the reported procedure⁷

The purity of the compounds was determined by mp, titration and C, H and N analyses. Metal was estimated by standard procedures⁸. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMSO) on CL 10A4 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured in dry DMSO using a Toshniwal CL01-10A conductivity meter at room temperature ($27 \pm 2^\circ$).

(2,6-Diacetylpyridine-N-iminodiacetylhydrazone) $Cu^{II}(BP_4)_2$. Equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of iminodiacetic acid dihydrazide, copper acetate and 2,6-diacetylpyridine were mixed in ethanol with continuous stirring. The mixture was refluxed over a water-bath for 7 h. It was then concentrated to one-third of its original volume under vacuum and a few crystals of sodium tetrafluoroborate were added to it and the solution was cooled overnight. The resulting light-green coloured crystals were washed with ethanol followed by ether and then dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

All other complexes were prepared by similar procedure.

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